

Niloofar Khandan, Nahhid Atghia, **Maryam Mokhtari Dinani**. (2018). [Relationship between Brand Personality and Consumer-based Brand Equity of Selected Football Clubs in Iranian Premier league](#), [Applied Research of Sport Management](#), 6 (24): 83-91.

Relationship between Brand Personality and Consumer-based Brand Equity of Selected Football Clubs in Iranian Premier League

N. Khandan, N. Atghia*, M. Mokhtari Dinani¹

1. MSc graduate of Sport Management, Alzahra University.
2. Associate Professor of Sport Management, Alzahra University.
3. Assistant Professor of Sport Management, Alzahra University.

Received: (02/Jan/2017) **Accepted:** (01/Jan/2018)

Abstract: The aim of this study was to identify the relationship between brand personality and consumer -based brand equity of football clubs in Iranian premier league. The samples of the present research include 405 members which are chosen randomly from 4 clubs consumers (direct members: 190 and indirect consumers: 215). Shafae et al (2013) brand personality questionnaire and brand equity questionnaire (based on Aker's model, 1991) was used to collect data. After collecting the data, for analyzing the findings, the statistical tests such as descriptive statistics, Kendall's tau-b, Friedman and Multiple Liner Regression were applied. The results showed that there is a significant positive relationship between all aspects of brand personality and brand equity. The value of R for excitement, Distinct and sophisticated were identified as the predictable elements of brand equity with the following impact factors 0.335, 0.269, 0.179.

Keywords: Brand, Football, Consumer

¹. Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@Alzahra.ac.ir